

Polymethin Dyes Derived from 6-Methylphenanthridine

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A number of polymethin dyes derived from 6-methyl-phenanthridine as the fixed basic nucleus have been prepared and their absorption maxima data were determined. The absorption maxima data have been utilised for determination of relative basicities of different basic nuclei as well as for determination of relative acidities of different acidic nuclei. These dyes are expected to be good photographic sensitisers.

THE present investigation deals with the preparation of some new polymethin dyes derived from 6-methyl-phenanthridine as the fixed basic nucleus. These dyes relate to the following general types :

- i) Symmetrical trimethin and pentamethin cyanines.
- ii) Unsymmetrical trimethin and pentamethin cyanines.
- iii) Dimethin merocyanines.
- iv) *p*-Dimethylaminostyryl dye and its aza-analogue.

The absorption maxima data of these dyes were determined and they are expected to be good photographic sensitisers. The details of their preparations are described in the experimental.

The relative basicity of 6-methylphenanthridine with respect to other basic nuclei has been determined with the help of Brooker's¹ 'Deviation Factor' by using the absorption maxima data of merocyanines derived from different basic nuclei and pyrazolone as the fixed acidic nucleus. According to Brooker in a series of merocyanines of a given chain length, the order of increasing deviations is the order of decreasing basicity of the variable basic nuclei constituting the dyes. The greater the deviation, the lower will be the basicity.

The deviations were calculated and described in Table-1 and the data indicate the following sequence in the order of basicities.

Quinoline-4 > 4-Phenylthiazole > Quinoline-2 >
6-Methylphenanthridine > Naphtho (2, 1-d)
thiazole > Benzothiazole > Benzoxazole.

TABLE 1—DEVIATION DATA OF DIMETHIN-MEROCYANINES DERIVED FROM 1-PHENYL-3-METHYL-PYRAZOLONE

Nucleus -B

Nature of nucleus 'B'	Absorption maximum in m μ			Calc. λ_{max} in m μ	Deviation in m μ
	Symm. methin oxonol	Symm. trimethin cyanine	Dimethin merocyanine		
Benzoxazole	443	480	447	461.5	14.5
Benzothiazole	443	565	490	504	14.0
Naphtho (2,1-d)-thiazole	443	590	508	516.5	8.5
6-Methylphenanthridine	443	610	522	526.5	4.5
Quinoline-2	443	610	523	526.5	3.5
4-Phenylthiazole:	443	565	501	504	3.0
Quinoline-4	443	710	587	576.5	-10.5

The magnitude of vinylene shifts in going from trimethin to pentamethin in the series of unsymmetrical cyanines derived from 6-methylphenanthridine as the fixed basic nucleus vary considerably with the nature of the other basic nucleus used.

The aza-analogue derived from 6-methylphenanthridine absorbs at a higher wave-length than the corresponding *p*-dimethylaminostyryl dye. This bathochromic shift of 75 m μ is in accordance with Forster's rule² and Knott's rule³.

Experimental

6-Methylphenanthridine was prepared by cyclisation of 2-acetamido-diphenyl with phosphorus oxychloride. Its methiodide was obtained by quarternisation with methyl iodide^{4,5}.

1. Symmetrical Trimethin & Pentamethin Cyanines :

(a) Bis(5-methylphenanthridine)-6,6'-trimethincyanine Iodide :

6-Methylphenanthridine methiodide (0.7g) and triethylorthoformate (0.45g) were boiled in acetic anhydride in presence of triethylamine (2 drops) for 5 minutes. Excess of acetic anhydride was removed under reduced pressure and on cooling the desired product separated out. It was recrystallised from absolute ethanol. Yield-40% ; m.p.-230°. (Found : I-22.85%, Formula requires I-23.0%). The dye shows maximum absorption at 615 m μ .

(b) Bis(5-methylphenanthridine)-6,6'-pentamethincyanine Iodide :

6-Methylphenanthridine methiodide (0.7g) and trimethoxypropene (0.15g) were boiled in acetic anhydride and triethylamine for 10 minutes. The product separated on cooling and recrystallised from absolute ethanol. Yield-30% ; m.p.-220°(d). (Found : I-21.81% Formula requires I-21.9%). The dye shows absorption maximum at 715 m μ .

2. *p*-Dimethylaminostyryl Dye and its Aza-Analogue.

(a) 6-*p*-Dimethylaminostyryl 5-methylphenanthridine Iodide :

6-Methylphenanthridine methiodide (0.7g) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.3g) were refluxed in redistilled acetic anhydride and piperidine (2 drops) for 10 minutes. After removal of excess of solvent under reduced pressure, the desired product separated on chilling as fine crystals. It was recrystallised from ethanol. Yield-80% ; m.p. 211°. (Found : C, 60.88%, H, 4.90%, Formula requires C, 61.8, H, 4.93%). The dye shows maximum absorption at 525 m μ .

(b) 6-*p*-Dimethylaminoanilino methylene-5-methylphenanthridine Iodide :

6-Methylphenanthridine methiodide (0.7g) and *p*-nitrosodimethyl aniline (0.3g) were refluxed in absolute ethanol in presence of piperidine (4 drops) for 30 minutes. The desired product separated on cooling and was subsequently recrystallised from ethanol. Yield-45% ; m.p.-220°. (Found : C, 58.85% ; H, 4.88%, Formula requires C, 59.1 ; H, 4.93%). The dye shows maximum absorption at 600 m μ .

3. Dimethin Merocyanines.

4-(3-Methylphenanthridine-6-Ylidene)-ethylidene-1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone :

4-(Acetanilidomethylene)-1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone (0.56g) and 6-methylphenanthridine methiodide (0.7g) were refluxed in ethanol and triethylamine for eight minutes. The product that separated on chilling was recrystallised from ethanol.

The analytical data etc⁶ of this dye and other dimethin merocyanines derived from 6-methylphenanthridine are given in Table-2.

4. Unsymmetrical Trimethin Cyanines :

The intermediate-6-(2-acetanilido vinyl) phenanthridine methiodide required for the synthesis of unsymmetrical trimethin cyanines was prepared by condensing 6-methylphenanthridine methiodide with diphenylformamide in acetic anhydride.

(5-Methylphenanthridine)(3-Methylbenzothiazole)-6,6'-trimethincyanine Iodide :

2-Methylbenzothiazole methiodide (0.6g) and 6-(2-acetanilidovinyl) phenanthridine methiodide (0.7g) were refluxed in absolute ethanol in presence of 2 drops of triethylamine for 5 minutes. The dye separated on cooling and was recrystallised from ethanol.

The analytical and absorption maxima data of this dye and other unsymmetrical trimethin cyanines derived from 6-methyl phenanthridine prepared in similar manner are given in Table-3.

5. Unsymmetrical Pentamethin Cyanines :

The intermediate 6-(4-acetanilido-1,3-butadienyl) phenanthridine methiodide required for the synthesis of unsymmetrical pentamethin cyanines was prepared by condensing 6-methylphenanthridine methiodide (2.8g) and β -anilino acrolein anil hydrochloride⁶ (2.58g) in acetic anhydride medium. Excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the product separated on cooling was washed with ether and was used directly for the dye formation without further purification.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND ABSORPTION DATA OF DIMETHIN MERCYANINES

Nature of nucleus 'A'	M. P. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Pyrazolone	170	45	522	79.65	79.79	5.18	5.37
4-Hydroxy-5 : 6-benzocoumarin	190 (d)	35	510	81.00	81.11	4.40	4.42
2-Phenyl-oxazolone	200 (d)	30	550	79.23	79.36	4.59	4.76
Thiazolone	210 (d)	40	564	70.81	70.91	4.51	4.54
Diphenylthiobarbituric acid	210	45	510	74.73	74.85	4.35	4.48
N-phenylthiohydantoin	240	45	515	73.12	73.34	4.50	4.64

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL AND ABSORPTION MAXIMA DATA OF UNSYMMETRICAL TRIMETHIN CYANINES

Nature of nucleus 'B'	M. P. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Benzothiazole	225	40	585	58.85	59.06	4.01	4.13
4-Phenyl-thiazole	195	45	580	60.18	60.67	4.19	4.31
Benzoxazole	231	30	550	60.91	60.97	4.16	4.26
Quinoline-2	190	35	605	64.35	64.54	4.49	4.58
Quinoline-4	150	40	650	64.53	64.54	4.51	4.58
Pyridine-2	>230	40	565	61.01	61.06	4.00	4.06
Pyridine-4	217	35	595	61.02	61.06	3.98	4.06
Naphtho (1,2-d) thiazole	183	50	602	62.32	62.36	4.01	4.12
Naphtho (2,1-d) thiazole	191	40	604	62.31	62.36	4.08	4.12
4,5-Diphenylthiazole	217	40	594	64.38	64.91	4.38	4.42
Benzo (f) quinoline	> 230	30	616	67.01	67.38	4.50	4.52
Thiazoline	> 230	25	525	54.58	54.78	4.51	4.58

TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL AND ABSORPTION MAXIMA DATA OF UNSYMMETRICAL TRIMETHIN CYANINES

Nucleus - B

Nature of nucleus 'B'	M. P. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} in m μ	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Benzothiazole	> 230	35	665	60.58	60.67	4.29	4.31
Benzoxazole	> 230	40	645	62.51	62.54	4.34	4.44
4-Phenylthiazole	190 (d)	30	660	62.10	62.14	4.38	4.46
Quinoline-2	197	25	688	65.80	65.91	4.67	4.74
Quinoline-4	> 230	25	710	65.88	65.91	4.58	4.74
Pyridine-2	> 230	25	625	62.71	62.76	4.78	4.81
Pyridine-4	200 (d)	25	655	62.58	62.76	4.80	4.81
Naphtho (1,2-d) thiazole	> 230	30	683	66.88	66.98	4.08	4.28
Naphtho (2,1-d)-thiazole	> 230	30	685	66.89	66.98	4.19	4.28
4,5-Diphenylthiazole	190 (d)	25	676	66.00	66.03	4.51	4.55
Benzo (f) quinoline	> 210	20	690	68.41	68.51	4.59	4.67
Thiazoline	—	20	625	56.68	56.79	4.65	4.73

(5-Methylphenanthridine)(3-methylbenzothiazole)-6,2'-pentamethincyanine Iodide :

6-(4-Acetanilido-1,3-butadienyl)-phenanthridine methiodide (0.4g) and 2-methylbenzothiazole methiodide (0.3g) were refluxed in absolute ethanol in presence of triethylamine for 10 minutes. Excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure and on chilling the desired dye separated out. It was recrystallised from ethanol.

The analytical and absorption maxima data of this dye and other unsymmetrical pentamethin cyanines derived from 6-methylphenanthridine prepared in similar manner are given in Table-4.

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